

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 3.3

List of Selected Proposals of 1st Internal Call

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

BPM	Board of programme Managers
MXX	EJP SOIL project months
WP	Work package

1. Submitted and evaluated proposals

1.1. General overview

The EJP SOIL will maximize the contribution of agricultural soil towards achieving sustainability at societal, scientific, operational, and policy levels. At the scientific level the EJP SOIL will i) quantify trade-offs and synergies between agricultural production, climate change adaptation and mitigation, ii) assess and validate practices to maintain soil fertility, soil health and other ecosystem services, iii) gather new knowledge on carbon sequestration in soils across Europe and their contribution to climate change mitigation, and iv) improve accounting and reporting tools for emission and removals from agricultural activities. Activities aiming to develop required knowledge will be supported by the EJP SOIL through specific research and innovation projects *via* internal (i.e. WP3 “Internal Calls”) and external EJP SOIL calls. The overall objective of the 1st internal call has been to fund stocktaking activities, syntheses and research projects open to EJP SOIL beneficiaries and linked third parties to fill research and development gaps identified by the EJP SOIL “Roadmap for EU Agricultural Soil Management research” and listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Topics of the EJP SOIL 1st Internal Call

Topic title	ID*	Number of projects and their size [#]
Quantification of the potential of agricultural soils to sequester more carbon at the regional / national scale in the different partner countries	CM2	1 large-sized
Evaluating soil management options for specific objectives: Trade-offs between soil organic carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emissions and/or N and P losses	CM8	2 medium-sized
Good knowledge of the present status of agricultural soils: Innovative techniques for soil mapping and assessing spatial and temporal variation of soil properties	MT1	2 medium-sized
Landscape analyses: Erosion processes	SR5	1 medium-sized
Enabling conditions to implement improved management options and tools to monitor soil quality: Analysis on how soil indicators could be used to support CAP measures	ES7 [†]	1 small-sized
Innovative soil management practices in Europe and their suitability for European farming systems	FS2/MT4	1 stock-taking
Methodologies and tools to assess the contribution of soils to ecosystem services / for assessing soil quality	ES1/ES2	1 stock-taking
Evaluating soil management options for the specific objective of climate change adaptation	CA1	1 synthesis

* Fist Internal Call Text, D3.2

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† No proposal submitted

The WP3 Call Office disseminated information on the call two times; a pre-announcement in M4 and publishing the full call text in M6 (Table 2) on the EJP SOIL website. Submission deadline was set as 18th September 2020. The call office received 11 proposals addressing at least one of the call topics, except ES7 (Tables 1 and 3). Most project proposals have been submitted by coordinators from Central and West Europe (~50%; Table 3), some by coordinators from South Europe (~30%) and North Europe

(~20%), but none of the submitted project proposals was coordinated by an EJP SOIL member from East and South East Europe. A brief overview of the submitted projects is shown in table 4 and at the end of this section (i.e. the project summaries drafted by the applicants). Out of the 11 proposals 10 passed the eligibility check (Table 5). Eligible proposals were reviewed by external evaluators between 27th September and 18th November, 2020. Final validation was done by the BPM in M10. Selected projects are expected to start in January 2021.

Table 2: Timeline of the EJP SOIL's 1st internal call

Action	Project calendar	Schedule
Call pre-announcement	M4	18 May 2020
Launch of the call	M5	30 June 2020
Webinar for interested applicants	M6	15 July 2020
Closing date for proposal submission	M8	18 September 2020
Proposal evaluation and selection	M8-M9	September - November 2020
Notification letters sent to project coordinators	M10	4 December 2020
Contract negotiations between consortium beneficiaries and linked third parties of medium and large projects	M11	December 2020
Start of research projects	M11-12	January 2021
End of research projects	-/-	Depends on project size

Table 3: Number of proposals submitted per call topics; proposal coordinator; country and regions of their home country

Topic ID	Number of applications	Proposal coordinator	Coordinator's European region
CM2	2	Thuenen / Germany TAGEM / Turkey	Central/West South
CM8	3	CREA / Italy INIA / Spain Luke / Finland	South South North
MT1	2	AgroParisTech / France AU / Denmark	Central/West North
SR5	1	BAW / Austria	Central/West
ES7	0	-/-	-/-
FS1/MT4	1	CRAW / Belgium	Central/West
ES1/ES2	1	WUR / Netherland	Central/West
CA1	1	ILVO / Belgium	Central/West
Total	11		

Table 4: Submitted and eligible proposals, their type, estimated budget and number of beneficiaries and linked third parties.

EJP ID	Acronym	Titel	Proposal coordinator	Type	Budget in kEUR	Number of beneficiaries	Number of linked third parties	Total number
CM2	CarboSeq	Soil organic carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils in Europe	Thuenen / Germany	large	4,023	21	6	27
CM8	SOMMIT	SUstainable Management of soil Organic Matter to MItigate Trade-offs between C sequestration and nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses	CREA / Italy	medium	1,730	7	6	13
CM8	TRACE-Soils	Mechanisms underlying TRAdE-offs between Carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas Emissions and nutrient losses in Soils under conservation agriculture in Europe	INIA / Spain	medium	1,603	6	2	8
CM8	INSURE	Indicators for carbon sequestration and successful greenhouse gas mitigation by rewetting cultivated peat soils	Luke / Finland	medium	1,703	5	1	6
MT1	STEROPES	Stimulating novel Technologies from Earth Remote Observation to Predict European Soil carbon	AgroParisTech / France	medium	1,712	11	1	12
MT1	SensRes	Sensor data for downscaling digital soil maps to higher resolution	AU / Denmark	medium	1,067	5	0	5
SR5	SCALE	Managing sediment connectivity in agricultural landscapes for reducing water erosion impacts	BAW / Austria	medium	1,750	6	7	13

EJP ID	Acronym	Titel	Proposal coordinator	Type	Budget in kEUR	Number of beneficiaries	Number of linked third parties	Total number
FS2/MT4	i-SoMPE	Innovative Soil Management Practices across Europe	CRAW / Belgium	stock-taking	457	23	2	25
ES1/ES2	SIREN	Stocktaking for Agricultural Soil Quality and Ecosystem Services Indicators and their Reference Values	WUR / Netherland	stock-taking	358	21	3	24
CA1	CLIMASO MA	CLIMAtE change adaptation through SOil and crop MAnagement: synthesis and ways forward	ILVO / Belgium	Synthesi s	218	5	0	5

Each project proposal was briefly described by the applicants; see their summaries below:

CM2 Carboseq: Carbon sequestration in soils is a negative emission technology that can contribute to mitigate climate change. However, for European soils, a comprehensive assessment is missing on how much soil organic carbon (SOC) can be sequestered with different management options using also national data on agricultural management. The aim of *CarboSeq* is thus to estimate the feasible SOC-sequestration potential taking into account technical and socio-economic constraints. The project will align with the current FAO activity for a global SOC-sequestration potential map (GSOCseq). The key for SOC-sequestration is an enhanced input of biomass (e.g. crop residues) to the soil. for which a new database will be built to facilitate model runs with RothC and other soil SOC models for different management scenarios. The potential area of implementation will be developed together with all partners of *CarboSeq* and the national expert hubs. All partners will run RothC at national levels. The SOC-sequestration potential maps for different management options will guide policy makers regional specific to the most efficient agricultural management options to sequester SOC for climate mitigation.

CM8 SOMMIT: The SOMMIT project will evaluate trade-offs and synergies between soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses as affected by soil management options aimed at increasing soil C storage. The integrated and interdisciplinary approach will address the main pedo-climatic conditions and farming systems in Europe, through 1) synthesis and meta-analysis of available literature and data; 2) targeted, novel measurements on key long-term experiments; and 3) simulation of long-term agro-ecological system responses to contrasting management options. Moreover, obtained data will be synthesized through a fuzzy-expert system which will allow for 4) evidence-based identification of optimal strategies for mitigation of trade-offs, and 5) effective stakeholders' involvement.

CM8 TRACE-Soils: Soil C sequestration in agroecosystems can promote soil quality and biodiversity, but come at a cost of increased nutrient losses and greenhouse gas emissions. Aiming to increase the predictability of such synergies and trade-offs, we will study their underlying mechanisms by reviewing

literature that quantifies them under different agricultural systems and management practices. We will identify soil abiotic and biotic predictors of trade-off magnitudes, and test them in long-term experiments across a NE-SW pedo-climatic gradient in Europe. Modelling scenarios will be posed to scale-up trade-off analysis to the provincial level. Outputs of reviews, experiments and models will serve to propose a ranked list of climate-zone specific indicators and measures to assess and mitigate trade-offs.

CM8 INSURE: Wet management with raised ground water table and flood-tolerant crops is an option to reduce peat decomposition and the related greenhouse gas emissions and water contamination from cultivated peatlands while still providing income for the farmers. However, there are sites with the risk of tradeoffs like high methane or phosphorus emissions diminishing the environmental benefits. Measurable indicators used in the selection of sites would increase the success rate of rewetting and thus the acceptability of wet agricultural management of peat soils. Experimental work together with modelling and advanced analysis of peat composition in INSURE project aims at improved understanding of controls of element cycling in rewetted ecosystems and to finding robust indicators for the tradeoffs of wet management.

MT1 STEROPES: Conventional high-detail soil maps are static and often based on obsolete data in relation to the time of use. STEROPES intends to overcome these limitations putting the use of satellite time series forward, to test their potential to predict cropland soil organic carbon content over various pedo-climatic conditions and cropping systems across Europe. First, models will be constructed from the reflectance image spectra of optical satellite series, notably Sentinel-2 (ESA), based on a number of diversified areas for which soil organic carbon samples are already available. The second phase of the project will be dedicated to analysing the influence of various factors on SOC prediction performance: soil moisture, texture, dry vegetation due to management practices, salinity. Then, for the sites where satellite information may not enable to derive acceptable predictions, other ancillary data will be considered at a more detailed scale, using geophysical proxies to reduce the uncertainty associated with these predictions.

MT1 SensRes: Soil maps for large areas often fail to account for local variation in soil properties, due to their coarse resolutions. However, remote and proximal sensors can provide highly detailed soil information at a local level. We therefore propose a method to downscale large-extent soil maps using sensor data. We will test the method for agricultural fields in seven European countries, using proximal sensors, drone images and satellite images. The mapped soil properties will include soil organic carbon, soil texture and locally important soil properties. We will test drone and satellite images of bare soils and vegetated fields, and we will test the effect of fusion data from different sensors. We will also test the potential for using the downscaled soil maps in practical applications.

SR5 SCALE: SCALE is a consortium of 13 research institutes from 9 EU-countries that aims to improve the management of sediment connectivity in diverse agricultural landscapes. It composes i) current state-of-the-art of connectivity principles in modelling and legal standards, ii) data set harmonisation, iii) harmonisation of up- and downscaling methods, iv) evaluation of on- and off-site measures and connectivity elements in common modelling approaches, v) development of frameworks with mitigation measures and best management practices for stakeholders and vi) the communication of the project's output. SCALE will significantly improve the harmonisation of data sets, observation and modelling techniques in connectivity research and bridge the gap between different spatial and administrative scales.

FS2/MT4 i-SomPE: Innovative soil management practices (SMP) and agricultural systems are promoted to enhance ecosystem services in order to minimise soil threats and sustain agriculture in a

climate change context. A comprehensive stocktake of SMPs and their ability to succeed on multiple goals, agricultural production, ecosystem services, biogeochemical cycles, is missing. By using a surveying approach, i-SomPE will aim to document these innovative farming practices. The data gathered will be synthesized considering technical and ecological constraints and socio-economic barriers. Context specific thematic maps will be provided to guide policy makers to the most efficient innovative SMPs as climate-smart sustainable tools.

ES1/ES2 SIREN: The SIREN project will make an inventory of indicator systems for assessing soil quality and ecosystem services, as currently used by Member States associated in the EJP SOIL and beyond. SIREN will identify and review the national frameworks and chains from soil properties via soil functions to soil ecosystem services and the indicators of soil quality state and functions plus their reference values across pedo-climatic conditions for the main agricultural production systems in the EU. Also, SIREN will identify if these have been translated into policy options and implementation, and into directions and guidance on land management. SIREN will particularly stocktake the array of reference values for SOC, soil quality, soil biodiversity and degradation risk, the associated target values of indicators, and identify knowledge gaps and development needs.

CA1 CLIMASOMA: Soil management and cropping systems to enhance soil quality are often proposed as a key way to support the sustainable adaptation of EU agriculture to climate change. Many long-term field trials quantified the impact of specific management practices on soil quality and crop performance. However, the data gathered there has not yet been sufficiently synthesized so that practitioners and policy-makers can draw quantitative and context-specific conclusions concerning the efficacy of management practices as climate adaptation tools. CLIMASOMA will directly contribute to an alignment of research strategies connecting agricultural management, soil quality and climate adaptation potential through its summary of the literature, its meta-analysis and its identification of knowledge gaps.

1.2. Eligibility check

Each submitted proposal was evaluated by WP3 against eligibility criteria described in the EJP SOIL 1st internal call text, section 4.2 (see D3.2):

- The application must be written in English.
- Applications must be complete and in accordance to the submission procedure.
- Applications must be submitted in time.
- Proposals including beneficiaries and/or third linked parties that are NOT EJP SOIL beneficiaries are not eligible to apply and will be rejected (see D3.2).

As mentioned above 10 out of 11 proposals passed the eligibility check. However, coordinators of the selected projects will be asked to revise ethics and communication sections of their proposals prior their project start.

1.3. Evaluation results and validation of the selection

WP3 built up a pool of external evaluators currently consisting of 39 experts (out of 100 that were invited) who agreed to evaluate EJP SOIL project proposals and signed a non-disclosure agreement. The evaluators cover multiple disciplines (e.g. soil organic carbon, soil nutrients, agronomy, peat soils, ICT) allowing discipline-specific evaluations. Each project proposal was evaluated by at least 3 external evaluators.

As mentioned in the EJP SOIL 1st call (section 4.4; see D3.2) a threshold of 3 out of 5 was applied for each criterion, i.e. proposals with a mean score <3 in any main criterion was not recommended for funding. None of the projects received for one of the evaluation criteria (i.e. Excellence, Impact, Implementation) an average score of <3.

The request to fund eligible and evaluated project proposals was validated by the BPM on 25th November 2020: Carboseq, STEREOPEs, SCALE, i-SoMPE, SIREN, CLIMASOMA were approved for funding. Considering the strategic interest of having projects dealing on the one hand with mineral soils and on the other hand with organic soils, the BPM validated to fund three projects under the topic CM3, instead of 2 as initially planned: SOMMIT, TRACE-Soils and INSURE. One of the proposals under MT1 topic: SensRES was validated conditionally; under condition, that applicant would improve the description of the methodology. As soon as the improvement is confirmed by the previous reviewers, the project will be funded. On 4th December notification letters were sent to the project coordinators.

